

ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ЛАПАРОСКОПІЧНОЇ АЛОПЛАСТИКИ ПУПКОВИХ ГРИЖ ПОЄДНАНИХ ІЗ ДІАСТАЗОМ ПРЯМИХ М'ЯЗІВ ЖИВОТА

FEATURES OF LAPAROSCOPIC ALOPLASTY OF UMBILICAL HERNIAS COMBINED WITH DIASTASIS OF THE RECTAL MUSCLES

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Background. In the structure of external abdominal hernias, the incidence of umbilical hernias is 8-19% and takes second place after inguinal hernias, and in 60% of cases, there is a combination of them with diastase of the rectus abdominis. The use of mesh implants for the surgical treatment of umbilical hernias with diastase of the rectus abdominis improves postoperative results. At the same time, the recurrence rate remains high at 10-15%. The main causes of recurrence of umbilical hernias associated with diastase of the rectus abdominis are insufficient or incomplete elimination of diastase of the rectus abdominis in alloplasty of umbilical hernias.

Purpose. To increase the effectiveness of surgical treatment of umbilical hernias associated with diastase of the rectus abdominis.

Materials and methods of research. The analysis of the surgical treatment of 82 patients with umbilical hernias combined with a diastase of rectus abdominis muscles is carried out. The average age was 56.1 ± 1.2 years. There were 52 women and 30 men. Depending on the method of surgical treatment, patients were divided into two groups. In group I (42 patients) - surgical treatment was performed according to an improved method of laparoscopic peritoneal allogeneic plastics with the elimination of diastase of the rectus abdominis by transfascial sutures. In group II (40 patients) - the traditional method of laparoscopic peritoneal allogeneic plastic surgery without elimination of diastase was performed. In the postoperative period, the frequency of postoperative complications and recurrences of umbilical hernia was assessed.

Results and discussions. Immediate results of surgical treatment of umbilical hernias associated with diastase of rectus abdominis among patients of group I (main) group (n=42) showed that seroma was observed in 3 (7%) and among patients of group II (comparison) in 2 (5%). Chronic postoperative pain in the umbilical region was diagnosed in 2 (%) patients of the main group and 1 (2%) of the comparison group. Long-term results of surgical treatment of umbilical hernias associated with diastasis of the rectus muscles were

studied by repeated examinations and questionnaires in the period from 1 to 3 years. Among 35 patients of group I recurrences of umbilical hernia were not detected, and among patients in comparison group 3 (8.6%) relapses were diagnosed. The obtained results showed higher efficiency of surgical treatment of umbilical hernias in patients of the main group, which was achieved through the use of the developed method of laparoscopic preperitoneal allogeneic plastics with the elimination of diastasis directly from the abdominal muscles.

Conclusion. Introduction of the developed method of laparoscopic alloplasty of umbilical hernias with the elimination of diastase of rectus muscles in comparison with traditional laparoscopic alloplasty reduces the probability of recurrence to 0% against 8.6%